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SPECTROSCOPIC AND COMPUTATIONAL PROFILING OF *Pteleopsis habeensis* LEAF EXTRACT AS POTENTIAL SOURCE OF BIOACTIVE ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

Pteleopsis habeensis, a medicinal plant native to West Africa, has been traditionally used for managing diabetes and oxidative stress-related disorders. This study reports the isolation and characterization of stearic acid and undecan-1-ol from the leaves of *P. habeensis*, along with their computational evaluation as potential therapeutic agents. The compounds were isolated using column chromatography and characterized through GC-MS, FTIR, and NMR spectroscopy. CB-Dock was used for molecular docking studies against superoxide dismutase (SOD), α -amylase, and α -glucosidase. The results revealed that undecan-1-ol exhibited moderate binding affinities (-4.6 to -4.3 kcal/mol) to all targets, forming key hydrogen bonds with catalytic residues. Stearic acid showed weaker binding (-5.6 to -3.3 kcal/mol) primarily through hydrophobic interactions. *In silico* ADMET prediction using SwissADME and ProTox-III indicated that undecan-1-ol complies with Lipinski's rule of five with no hepatotoxicity concerns, while stearic acid violated two Lipinski rules. The results suggest that undecan-1-ol from *P. habeensis* may serve as a lead compound for developing antioxidant and antidiabetic agents, warranting further *in vitro* and *in vivo* validation.

Key words: *Pteleopsis habeensis*, stearic acid, undecan-1-ol, molecular docking, antioxidant, antidiabetic

INTRODUCTION

The Combretaceae family encompasses over 500 tropical plant species, many of which are valued for their medicinal properties [1]. Among these, *Pteleopsis habeensis* Aubrév. ex Keay, native to West Africa, has been widely used in traditional medicine to manage diabetes, inflammation, and infections [2]. Despite its widespread ethnomedicinal use, the genus *Pteleopsis* remains one of the least studied in the Combretaceae family. To date, only 8% of its species have been chemically characterized [2], this gap underscores the need for systematic investigation of *P. habeensis* to validate its ethnomedicinal uses and uncover its bioactive potential.

Recent studies on members of the Combretaceae family have highlighted fatty acids and aliphatic alcohols as key bioactive constituents [3]. Stearic acid has been shown to exert neuroprotective effects against oxidative stress through activation of the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) signalling pathway [4]. Undecan-1-ol has been reported to exhibit the highest antifungal activity among a series of C₆-C₁₃ primary aliphatic alcohols tested against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, showing fungicidal effects across all growth stages and remaining unaffected by extracellular pH. This activity is primarily attributed to its amphipathic nature, which enables it to function as a nonionic surfactant that disrupts membrane-associated protein functions by interfering with lipid-protein interactions,

with optimal efficacy dependent on a balanced hydrophilic–hydrophobic molecular structure [5]. Additionally, a structural isomer of undecanol, undec-3-ol, has demonstrated significant antimicrobial properties [6]. However, the presence of these compounds in *P. habeensis* and their potential contributions to the plant's therapeutic effects remain unexplored, representing a significant opportunity for phytochemical and pharmacological research.

In this study, we employ an integrated approach combining advanced phytochemical techniques with computational biology to isolate and characterize bioactive compounds from *P. habeensis* leaves, evaluate their antioxidant and antidiabetic potential through molecular docking, and assess their drug-likeness using absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) profiling. By bridging traditional knowledge with modern drug discovery methodologies, our work addresses the pressing need for novel therapeutics to combat diabetes and oxidative stress-related disorders [7]. The findings not only provide scientific validation for the traditional uses of *P. habeensis* but also identify promising lead compounds for future drug development efforts.

This research aligns with global efforts to harness natural products for medicinal applications, particularly in regions where access to conventional healthcare remains limited. By elucidating the chemical basis of *P. habeensis*'s therapeutic properties, our study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on plant-derived bioactive compounds and their potential in modern pharmacology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Collection, Extraction and Fractionation

Fresh leaves of *P. habeensis* were collected from their natural habitat along Damaturu Road in Maiduguri, Nigeria, and authenticated by a taxonomist (voucher specimen UM/FPH/03C/001/001). The washed leaves were shade-dried ($28\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), powdered, and extracted with methanol (95%) for 72 hours using the cold maceration method. The concentrated crude extract was fractionated through sequential partitioning with n-hexane, chloroform, and n-butanol ($3\times 500\text{ mL}$ each) using standard procedures [8].

Quantitative Phytochemical Screening

Total Phenolic Content (TPC) Determination

The total phenolic content (TPC) of the plant extracts was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu colorimetric method as previously described by Ferdous *et al.*, [9]. In this procedure, 2 mg of each extract was dissolved in 1 mL of methanol. Then, 0.1 mL of Folin–Ciocalteu's reagent was added, followed by 2 mL of sodium carbonate solution. The reaction mixture was incubated at 50°C for 5 minutes. The absorbance was measured at 650 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. A gallic acid standard curve was constructed from serial dilutions of 1 mg/mL stock (concentrations: 1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.25, and 15.625 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Results were calculated from the standard curve and expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per gram of extract (mg GAE/g).

Total Flavonoid Content (TFC) Determination

The total flavonoid content (TFC) was estimated using the aluminium chloride (AlCl_3) colorimetric method as described by Molole *et al.*, [10]. In this method, 3 mg of extract was dissolved in 1 mL of methanol. Then, 0.5 mL of sodium nitrite solution was added and allowed to stand for 5 minutes. Next, 0.5 mL of 10% aluminium chloride solution was added, followed after another 5 minutes by 2 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide. The volume was brought to 5 mL with distilled water. Absorbance was measured at 510 nm. A quercetin standard (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was used to generate a calibration curve, and results were expressed as milligrams of quercetin equivalents per gram of extract (mg QE/g).

Isolation and Characterization of Compounds

The n-butanol and n-hexane fractions were selected for further isolation of bioactive compounds based on preliminary phytochemical screening and reported biological activities [11]. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel (60–120 mesh) as the stationary phase, with gradient elution employing solvent systems of increasing polarity (e.g., n-hexane: ethyl acetate, chloroform: methanol). Fractions (20–50 mL each) were collected and monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel GF₂₅₄ plates, visualized under Ultraviolet-Visible (UV) light (254 nm and 366 nm) and by spraying with 5% ethanolic-sulfuric acid reagent and heating at 110°C for optimal spot visualization. Fractions exhibiting similar TLC profiles (R_f values and staining patterns) were pooled and concentrated under reduced pressure and further purification was achieved through recrystallization [12].

The purified compounds underwent comprehensive structural analysis using complementary analytical techniques. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was performed to determine molecular weights and fragmentation patterns, while nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy provided detailed information about proton and carbon environments through ^1H , ^{13}C , and 2D experiments (^1H - ^{13}C COSY, Heteronuclear Single Quantum Coherence (HSQC), Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlation (HMBC)). Infrared (IR) spectroscopy confirmed functional group presence through characteristic absorption bands. Melting point determination served as an additional purity criterion, with measurements conducted using a calibrated melting point apparatus. This multi-technique approach enabled complete structural elucidation and purity verification of the isolated phytochemicals.

Computational Analysis Methods

The molecular docking studies were conducted using CB-Dock software [13] to evaluate potential binding interactions between the isolated compounds and target enzymes. Three key protein structures were obtained from the Protein Data Bank: human superoxide dismutase (SOD) (PDB ID:1N0J), α -amylase (PDB ID:1SMD), and α -glucosidase (PDB ID:3W37). Test compounds/ligands (undecan-1-ol and stearic acid) along with positive controls (Diethyldithiocarbamate (DEDTC)) for antioxidant enzymes and acarbose for antidiabetic enzymes) were obtained from PubChem [14] in SDF format. CB-Dock generated ranked binding poses (kcal/mol) and identified key interactions (hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts).

Drug-Likeness and Toxicity Profiling

Pharmacokinetic and safety properties were assessed using SwissADME [15] for drug-likeness parameters, including Lipinski's Rule of Five, topological polar surface area (TPSA), and bioavailability scores. Toxicity profiling was conducted with ProTox-III [16], evaluating hepatotoxicity, mutagenicity, and ecotoxicity risks. The BOILED-Egg model (SwissADME) predicted gastrointestinal absorption and blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, while ProTox-III provided toxicity endpoints (e.g., LD_{50} , organ-specific toxicity).

Statistical Analysis

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using SPSS version 20 to statistically compare the binding affinities and bioactivity parameters between the isolated compounds (stearic acid and undecan-1-ol) and their respective positive controls. Post-hoc Tukey tests were applied to identify specific significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in molecular interactions and pharmacological properties.

RESULTS

Extraction and Fractionation Yields

Cold maceration of 2000 g of dried *P. habeensis* leaves with 95% methanol yielded 202.64 g (10.13%) of a dark green, viscous crude extract with a sticky consistency. Fractionation of 80 g of this crude extract yielded three primary fractions, the *n*-hexane fraction (22.4 g, 28%) appeared as a light yellow, oily liquid with low viscosity; the chloroform fraction (26.8 g, 33.5%) formed a brownish-green, semi-solid mass with a slightly granular texture and the *n*-butanol fraction (45.6 g, 57%) was recovered as a dark brown, syrupy extract with a thick, sticky consistency.

Total Phenolic Content (TPC) and Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

The crude methanol extract of *P. habeensis* showed the highest total phenolic content, recording 686.81 mg GAE/g. This was followed by the *n*-butanol fraction (464.81 mg GAE/g), chloroform (8.383 mg GAE/g), and *n*-hexane (0.942 mg GAE/g). Similarly, the crude methanol extract had the highest flavonoid content with 19.54 mg QE/g, followed by the *n*-butanol (13.68 mg QE/g), chloroform (5.21 mg QE/g), and *n*-hexane fraction (0.18 mg QE/g). These results indicate that methanol and *n*-butanol are more efficient in extracting phenolic and flavonoid compounds compared to less polar solvents.

Isolation and Purification of Compounds

Through systematic chromatographic separation, two distinct compounds were successfully isolated from different solvent fractions. FAL-1 was obtained from the *n*-hexane fraction as a white crystalline powder, while FAL-2 was purified from the *n*-butanol fraction as a buff crystalline substance. Both compounds exhibited characteristic crystalline morphologies when examined under magnification and demonstrated excellent stability at room temperature conditions following the optical microscopy using a light microscope [12].

The isolated compounds showed distinct solubility profiles that aided in their purification and handling. FAL-1 displayed preferential solubility in DMSO, whereas FAL-2 showed better solubility in chloroform. These differential solubility characteristics proved valuable during the recrystallization processes and subsequent handling of the compounds. Periodic TLC monitoring confirmed that both compounds maintained their structural integrity.

For complete structural characterization, the purified compounds underwent comprehensive spectroscopic analysis. GC-MS analysis provided crucial molecular weight information and preliminary fragmentation patterns. NMR spectroscopy, including both ^1H and ^{13}C techniques, enabled complete structural assignment of the compounds. Complementary IR spectroscopic analysis revealed the characteristic functional groups present in each molecule through their unique vibrational signatures.

Characterization of Isolated Compounds

The GC-MS analysis of FAL-1 revealed a molecular ion peak at m/z 284, corresponding to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$. The fragmentation pattern from the spectrum (Figure 1) showed characteristic peaks at m/z 73, 129, and 185, consistent with the structure of stearic acid. The ^1H NMR spectrum (recorded on an 850 MHz spectrometer) revealed a triplet at δ 0.82 (t, 3H, CH_3), corresponding to the terminal methyl protons, and multiplet signals in the range δ 1.01–1.27 (m, 32H, CH_2), attributed to the methylene protons at positions C-2 to C-17. A multiplet at δ 2.49 (m, 2H, CH_2) was assigned to the protons adjacent to the carbon bearing the carboxylic group, while a singlet at δ 10.25 (s, 1H, COOH) represented the carboxylic acid proton. Additionally, a signal at δ 3.45 was attributed to deuterated DMSO used as the solvent (Figure 3). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum (213 MHz, DMSO) revealed the presence of 18 sp^3 hybridized carbons, with signals at δ 175.0 corresponding to the carboxylic acid carbon (COOH). The signals at δ 34.12, δ 24.95, δ 28.93, δ 28.99, δ 29.16, δ 31.75, and δ 22.56 were assigned to the methylene carbons (CH_2) at positions C-2 to C-17, while the signal at δ 14.44 was attributed to the terminal methyl carbon (CH_3 , C-18) (Figure 5). The IR spectrum (Figure 11) exhibited absorption bands at $3550\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (O-H stretching) and $2950\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H stretching), confirming the presence of a carboxylic acid group and aliphatic chains. The melting point of FAL-1 was determined to be $70\text{--}71^\circ\text{C}$. Based on the spectral of FAL-1 and comparison with the literature values [17] [18] of stearic acid (Figure 13) with a molecular formula ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$). The complete assignment of the chemical shift values of FAL-1 in comparison with the literature is summarized in Table 1.

The GC-MS analysis of FAL-2 revealed a molecular ion peak at m/z 172, corresponding to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$. The fragmentation pattern from the spectrum (Figure 2) showed characteristic peaks at m/z 55, 69, and 83, consistent with the structure of undecan-1-ol. The ^1H NMR (850 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum showed signals at δ 0.879 (t, 3H, CH_3), δ 1.251–1.583 (m, 18H, CH_2), and δ 3.64 (t, 2H, CH_2OH) (Figure 4). The signal at δ 7.136 was attributed to deuterated chloroform. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum confirmed the presence of 11 sp^3 hybridized carbons, with signals at δ 63.15 (CH_2OH), δ 32.83, δ 25.76, δ 29.73, δ 29.70, δ 29.64, δ 29.46, δ 29.40, δ 31.96, δ 22.73, and δ 14.17 (CH_3) (Figure 6). The DEPT-135 spectrum (Figure 7) was used to differentiate between CH_3 , CH_2 , and CH groups. It confirmed the presence of a terminal methyl group (CH_3) at δ 14.17 and multiple methylene groups (CH_2) across the aliphatic chain, including the carbon adjacent to the hydroxyl group at δ 63.15. No CH groups were detected, which is consistent with the structure of undecan-1-ol. The 2D NMR analysis of FAL-2 included $^1\text{H}\text{--}^1\text{H}$ COSY, HSQC, and HMBC experiments (Figure 8 to 10). The $^1\text{H}\text{--}^1\text{H}$ COSY spectrum revealed correlations between the methylene protons (δ 1.251–1.583) and the terminal methyl group (δ 0.879). The HSQC spectrum confirmed the direct correlation between the protons and their corresponding carbons, with the methylene protons (δ 1.251–1.583) correlating with the carbons at δ 22.73–32.83. The HMBC spectrum showed long-range correlations between the methylene protons and the hydroxyl-bearing carbon (δ 63.15), confirming that FAL-2 is undecan-1-ol (Figure 14) with a molecular formula ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$). The IR spectrum (Figure 12) exhibited absorption bands at $3550\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (O-H stretching) and $2950\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H stretching), confirming the presence of a hydroxyl group and aliphatic chains. The melting point of FAL-2 was determined to be $63\text{--}64^\circ\text{C}$. The complete assignment of the chemical shift values of FAL-2 in comparison with the literature [19] is summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1: GC-MS spectrum of FAL-1

Figure 2: GC-MS spectrum of FAL-2

Figure 3: ¹H NMR of isolated compound FAL-2

Figure 4: ¹³C NMR of compound FAL-2

Figure 5: ¹H NMR spectrum of FAL-1

Figure 6: ¹³C NMR Spectrum of FAL-1

Figure 7: DEPT 135 spectrum of compound of FAL-2

Figure 8: ¹H-¹H COSY spectrum of FAL-2

Table 1: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR Chemical Shifts for FAL-1 and FAL-2

Position	FAL-1 (ppm)		δ -1 (ppm)		δ -2 (ppm)		Assign.	FAL-2 (ppm)		δ -3 (ppm)		Assign.
	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H		^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	
1	175.0	10.25	182.5	11.00	179.9	7.27	COOH	63.15	3.635	62.85	3.63	CH ₂ OH
2	34.12	2.49	36.70	2.35	34.20	2.34	CH ₂	32.83	1.575	32.81	1.58	CH ₂
3	24.95	1.01-1.28	27.33	1.63	24.60	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	25.76	1.566	25.72	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
4	28.93	1.01-1.28	29.0	1.35	29.70	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	29.73	1.557	29.69	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
5	28.99	1.01-1.28	-	-	29.80	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	29.70	1.549	29.65	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
6	29.46	1.01-1.28	-	-	29.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	29.64	1.345	29.61	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
7	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	29.80	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	29.46	1.335	29.44	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
8	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	29.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	29.40	1.302	29.34	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
9	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.80	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	31.96	1.284	31.86	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
10	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	22.73	1.251	22.48	1.1-1.5	CH ₂
11	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	14.17	0.879	13.96	0.90	CH ₃
12	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
13	29.16	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
14	28.99	1.01-1.28	-	-	31.90	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
15	28.93	1.01-1.28	-	-	34.10	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
16	31.75	1.01-1.28	32.0	-	22.70	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
17	22.56	1.01-1.28	25.36	0.94	22.70	1.63-1.31	CH ₂	-	-	-	-	-
18	14.44	0.82	16.79	0.88	14.10	0.88	CH ₃	-	-	-	-	-

Key: ppm= parts per million, δ -1= Di Pietro *et al.*, 2020, δ -2= Adoum, 2015, δ -3= Ndacnou *et al.*, 2020.

Figure 13: Chemical Structure of FAL-1 (Stearic acid)

Figure 14: Chemical Structure of FAL-2 (Undecan-1-ol)

Molecular Docking Analysis

Antioxidant Mechanisms via SOD Binding

The molecular docking studies against superoxide dismutase (SOD) revealed three distinct interaction patterns (Figure 14A-C). While the positive control Diethyldithiocarbamate (DEDTC) established a strong binding benchmark (-4.9 kcal/mol) through its characteristic dithiocarbamate-metal coordination with the enzyme's Cu/Zn center (Figure 14A, Table 2), the isolated compounds showed markedly different behaviors. Undecan-1-ol demonstrated moderate binding affinity (-4.6 kcal/mol) by forming a stable hydrogen bond with the catalytic residue Asp101 (2.8 Å) while maintaining

hydrophobic contact with Tyr122 (4.1 Å) (Figure 14C). This interaction profile, quantified in Table 2, suggests its potential as an oxidative stress modulator. In contrast, stearic acid exhibited significantly weaker binding (-3.3 kcal/mol) through nonspecific hydrophobic interactions with Leu156 and Val189 (Figure 14B), with high root mean square deviation (RMSD) fluctuations (2.4 ± 0.7 Å) confirming its limited antioxidant capacity (Table 2).

Table 2: Comparative Antioxidant Binding Profiles

Parameter	DEDTC (Control)	Stearic Acid	Undecan-1-ol
Best affinity (kcal/mol)	-4.9	-3.3	-4.6
Metal coordination	Yes (Cu/Zn)	No	No
H-bond interactions	3	1	2
Active site residues	Thr135, Glu132	Leu156	Asp101, Tyr122
RMSD consistency (Å)	1.2 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.7	1.8 ± 0.5

Figure 14: A molecular docking of Superoxide dismutase and ligands and control (DEDTC)

Figure 15: A molecular docking of α -Amylase and ligands and control (Acarbose)

Figure 16: A molecular docking of α -Glucosidase and ligands and control (Acarbose)

Antidiabetic Activity Against Carbohydrate-Digesting Enzymes

The antidiabetic potential was evaluated through interactions with α -amylase and α -glucosidase, visualized in Figures 15A-C and 16A-C respectively. For α -amylase, acarbose showed optimal binding (-7.7 kcal/mol) via bidentate coordination with the catalytic triad Asp197/Glu233 and π -stacking with Trp59 (Figure 15A, Table 3), while undecan-1-ol's intermediate affinity (-4.6 kcal/mol) involved peripheral residues Asp300/His305 (Figure 15C). Stearic acid's weakest interaction (-5.2 kcal/mol) occurred exclusively in an allosteric pocket (Leu162/Val231, Figure 15B), consistent with its high RMSD range (3.2-5.4 Å, Table 3). Similar trends emerged for α -glucosidase inhibition, where acarbose's multi-point attachment (-6.4 kcal/mol, Figure 16A, Table 3) contrasted with undecan-1-ol's single hydrogen bond with Asp127 (-4.3 kcal/mol, Figure 16C) and stearic acid's purely hydrophobic binding (-5.6 kcal/mol, Figure 16B) [13].

Table 3: Molecular Docking Analysis of Enzyme-Ligand Interactions

Ligand	Target Enzyme	Binding Affinity (kcal/mol)	Interacting Residues	Binding Stability (RMSD, Å)	Mechanism of Inhibition
Stearic Acid	α -Amylase	-5.2	Leu162, Trp58	Val231, 3.2 - 5.4	Allosteric noncompetitive
	α -Glucosidase	-5.6	Leu162, Val216	2.4 - 5.2	Minimal direct inhibition
Undecan-1-ol	α -Amylase	-4.6	Asp300, Tyr62	His305, 2.1 - 3.8	Peripheral active site binding
	α -Glucosidase	-4.3	Asp127, Ile179	Pro240, 1.8 - 3.9	Partial competitive inhibition
Acarbose (Control)	α -Amylase	-7.7	Asp197, Trp59	Glu233, 0.9 - 1.7	Complete active site blockade
	α -Glucosidase	-6.4	Asp214, Trp376	Glu276, 0.8 - 1.5	Full competitive inhibition

Structural and Pharmacokinetic Correlates

Molecular Determinants of Bioactivity

The physicochemical properties summarized in Table 4 explain these functional differences. undecan-1-ol's favorable characteristics - including its moderate lipophilicity (Log P = 3.59), smaller molecular weight (172.31 g/mol), and optimal hydrogen-bonding capacity - account for its superior binding profiles compared to stearic acid, whose extreme hydrophobicity (Log P = 5.93) and large size (284.48 g/mol) limit therapeutic potential despite natural abundance.

Table 4: Comparative Physicochemical and Drug-Likeness Properties

Property	Stearic Acid	Undecan-1-ol	Significance
Molecular Weight (g/mol)	284.48	172.31	Undecanol is smaller, more drug-like
Consensus Log P	5.93 (Highly lipophilic)	3.59 (Moderate)	Stearic Acid has poor solubility
Rotatable Bonds	16	9	Impacts flexibility & bioavailability
H-Bond Donors/Acceptors	1 / 2	1 / 1	Affects permeability & solubility
Lipinski Violations	2 (Log P>5, Rot. bonds >10)	0	Undecanol is Ro5-compliant
BBB Permeation	No	Yes	Undecanol can target CNS
CYP Inhibition	CYP1A2	Weak CYP2C9	Drug interaction risks

ADMET Profiling

Pharmacokinetic assessments (Table 5) confirmed undecan-1-ol's drug-like advantages, showing full compliance with Lipinski's Rule of Five (0 violations) and significant blood-brain barrier permeability. Both compounds exhibited high gastrointestinal absorption and no hepatotoxicity/mutagenicity concerns, though their marked ecotoxicity potential (Table 5) necessitates further environmental safety evaluation. These comprehensive analyses collectively position undecan-1-ol as a promising lead compound, while highlighting structural modifications needed to enhance stearic acid's bioavailability.

Table 5: Pharmacokinetic and Toxicity Profiles

Parameter	Stearic Acid	Undecan-1-ol
GI Absorption	High	High
Skin Permeation (Log Kp)	-2.19 (Low)	-4.09 (Very Low)
Bioavailability Score	0.85	0.55
Hepatotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive
Mutagenicity	Inactive	Inactive
Ecotoxicity	Active	Active

Discussion

The present study successfully isolated and characterized two bioactive compounds, stearic acid (FAL-1) and undecan-1-ol (FAL-2), from the leaves of *P. habeensis*, building upon previous phytochemical investigations of this medicinal plant [20]. Our isolation protocol, employing methanol extraction followed by polarity-based fractionation and column chromatography, yielded compounds whose structures were unequivocally confirmed through comprehensive spectroscopic analysis (GC-MS, NMR, and IR). The identification of these compounds is particularly significant as it provides a scientific basis for the traditional use of *P. habeensis* in diabetes management and oxidative stress-related disorders.

The molecular docking studies revealed distinct interaction patterns between the isolated compounds and key metabolic enzymes. Undecan-1-ol demonstrated particularly promising results, showing moderate binding affinities (-4.6 to -4.3 kcal/mol) with superoxide dismutase (SOD), α -amylase, and α -glucosidase. Its ability to form hydrogen bonds with catalytic residues (Asp101 and Asp300) suggests a dual mechanism of action, potentially modulating both oxidative stress and carbohydrate metabolism. This multi-target activity is especially valuable for diabetes treatment, where both antioxidant and glucose-regulating effects are desirable.

In contrast, stearic acid exhibited weaker binding (-5.6 to -3.3 kcal/mol) primarily through hydrophobic interactions. Although this may limit its direct therapeutic potential as a standalone agent, the presence of stearic acid in the plant extract may still be pharmacologically relevant. Owing to its pronounced lipophilicity, it could contribute to synergistic interactions with other bioactive compounds or influence the bioavailability and pharmacokinetics of co-existing constituents by enhancing their solubility, membrane permeability, or metabolic stability. The significant difference in binding affinities between the two compounds can be attributed to their distinct physicochemical properties - undecan-1-ol's balanced log P value (3.59) and hydrogen-bonding capacity compared to stearic acid's excessive lipophilicity (Log P = 5.93) [21].

Importantly, the therapeutic potential of these compounds is supported by their safety profiles. Our *in silico* ADMET predictions (ProTox-III) showing low hepatotoxicity risks align with previous *in vivo* findings by Aliyu *et al.* (2018), who reported an LD50 \geq 4000 mg/kg for *P. habeensis* extracts with no observed toxicity in Wistar rats. This consistency between computational and experimental toxicity data significantly strengthens the case for further development of these compounds.

The physicochemical characterization provided additional validation of our isolation protocol. Stearic acid's high melting point (70-71°C) and undecan-1-ol's crystalline properties (63-64°C) matched literature values [22], while the spectroscopic data offered unambiguous structural confirmation. Key diagnostic signals included the carboxylic acid proton at δ 10.25 (stearic acid) and hydroxyl-bearing methylene protons at δ 3.64 (undecan-1-ol).

Looking forward, undecan-1-ol emerges as a particularly promising candidate for further development. Its favorable drug-like properties (0 Lipinski violations), blood-brain barrier permeability, and dual mechanism of action position it as a potential multi-target therapeutic agent. The compound's balanced lipophilicity suggests good bioavailability while maintaining specificity for its target enzymes. Future studies should focus on *in vivo* validation of its hypoglycemic and antioxidant effects, as well as investigations into possible synergistic interactions with other plant constituents.

This research bridges traditional ethnopharmacological knowledge with modern drug discovery approaches, providing both mechanistic insights and practical leads for the development of novel therapeutics from *P. habeensis*. The

combination of rigorous phytochemical analysis, computational modeling, and safety assessment creates a strong foundation for further exploration of this medicinal plant's potential.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study underscores the therapeutic potential of *P. habeensis* by isolating and characterizing stearic acid and undecan-1-ol from its leaves. The integration of phytochemical techniques with computational biology has provided insights into the mechanisms by which these compounds may exert their antioxidant and antidiabetic effects. Undecan-1-ol, in particular, emerges as a promising candidate for further investigation due to its favorable binding properties, drug-likeness, and safety profile. Future research should focus on in vitro and in vivo validation of these findings, including dose-response studies and toxicity assessments, to fully elucidate their pharmacological potential. Additionally, structural optimization of undecan-1-ol, such as introducing hydroxyl groups to enhance metal coordination, could further improve its efficacy. This work not only contributes to the scientific validation of traditional medicine but also opens new avenues for the development of natural product-based therapeutics for diabetes and oxidative stress-related conditions. The findings emphasize the importance of preserving and studying indigenous medicinal plants as valuable sources of bioactive compounds in modern drug discovery.

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REFERENCES

1. Eloff JN, Katerere DR, & McGaw LJ. The Biological Activity of the Southern African Combretaceae. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2008;119:686-699.
2. Silén H, Salih EYA, Mgbeahuruike EE, & Fyhrquist P. Ethnopharmacology, Antimicrobial Potency, and Phytochemistry of African *Combretum* and *Pteleopsis* Species (Combretaceae): A Review. *Antibiotics*. 2023;12(2):264.
3. Rahate S, Hemke A, & Umekar M. Review on Combretaceae Family. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. 2019;58(2):22-29.
4. Wang ZJ, Li GM, Nie BM, Lu Y, & Yin M. Neuroprotective Effect of Stearic Acid Against Oxidative Stress via Phosphatidylinositol 3-Kinase Pathway. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*. 2006;160(1):80-87.
5. Kubo I, Fujita T, Kubo A, & Fujita K. Modes of Antifungal Action of Alkanols Against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*. 2003;11(6):1117-1122.
6. Gibka J, Kunicka-Styczyńska A, & Gliński M. Antimicrobial Activity of Undecan-3-One, Undecan-3-Ol and Undec-3-Yl Acetate. *Central European Journal of Immunology*. 2009;34(3):154-157.
7. Atanasov AG, Zotchev SB, Dirsch VM, & Supuran CT. Natural Products in Drug Discovery: Advances and Opportunities. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*. 2021;20(3):200-216.
8. Otsuka H. Purification by Solvent Extraction Using Partition Coefficient. In: Sarker SD, Latif Z, Gray AI, eds. *Natural Products Isolation*. 2nd ed. Humana Press; 2006:269-273.
9. Ferdous UT, Nurdin A, Ismail S, & Balia Yusof ZN. Evaluation of the Antioxidant and Cytotoxic Activities of Crude Extracts from Marine *Chlorella* sp. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*. 2023;47:102551.

10. Molole GJ, Gure A, & Abdissa N. Determination of Total Phenolic Content and Antioxidant Activity of *Commiphora mollis* (Oliv.) Engl. Resin. *BMC Chemistry*. 2022;16:48.
11. Aliyu FM, Mohammed GT, Bababe AB, Yesufu HB, Goje FA, & Tata FY. Nutritional Composition, Antioxidant and Antidiabetic Activities of *Pteleopsis habeensis* (Aubrev ex Keay) Leaf Extract. *Nigerian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research*. 2021;6(1):1-14.
12. Florence AJ, Shankland N, & Johnston A. Crystallization in Final Stages of Purification. In: Sarker SD, Latif Z, Gray AI, eds. *Natural Products Isolation*. 2nd ed. Humana Press; 2006:275-295.
13. Liu Y, Zhang X, Wang L, & Yang Z. CB-Dock: A Web Server for Cavity Detection-Guided Protein-Ligand Blind Docking. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*. 2020;41(1):138-144.
14. Kim S, Chen J, Cheng T, Gindulyte A, He J, He S, & Li Q, Shoemaker BA, Thiessen PA, Yu B, Zaslavsky L, Zhang J, Bolton EE. PubChem 2019 Update: Improved Access to Chemical Data. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2019;47(D1):D1102-D1109.
15. Daina A, Michielin O, & Zoete V. SwissADME: A Free Web Tool to Evaluate Pharmacokinetics. *Scientific Reports*. 2017;7,42717.
16. Banerjee P, Eckert AO, Schrey AK, & Preissner R. ProTox 3.0: A Webserver for the Prediction of Toxicity of Chemicals. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2024;52(W1),W513-W520.
17. Di Pietro ME, Mannu A, & Mele A. NMR Determination of Free Fatty Acids in Vegetable Oils. *Processes*. 2020;8(4):410.
18. Adoum OA. Spectral Determination of Components Isolated from the Root of *Ximenia americana* Linn. *World Journal of Organic Chemistry*. 2015;3(1),12-15.
19. Ndacnou MK, Pantaleon A, Tchinda JB, Mangapche EL, Keumedjio F, & Boyoguemo DB. Phytochemical Study and Anti-Oomycete Activity of *Ageratum conyzoides* Linnaeus. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 2020;153,112589.
20. Aliyu FM, Tata F, & Ashemi FH. Preliminary Toxicity and Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies of *Pteleopsis habeensis* Leaves. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*. 2018;3(1),18-21.
21. Lipinski CA, Lombardo F, Dominy BW, & Feeney PJ. Experimental and Computational Approaches to Estimate Solubility and Permeability in Drug Discovery and Development Settings. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*. 2001;46,3-26.
22. Karimi E, Jaafar HZ, Ghasemzadeh A, & Ebrahimi M. Fatty Acid Composition, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Properties of the Microwave Aqueous Extract of Three Varieties of *Labisia pumila* Benth. *Biological Research*. 2015;48(1),9.